

EFFECT OF DIRECTORS TUNNELING ON MAINTENANCE COST OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY SERVICE INDUSTRIES IN NIGERIA

¹Abazu M. Ebere and ²Prof., M.S Ifureze

^{1,2}Department of Accountancy, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam, Anambra State Nigeria

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19815975>

Keywords: directors tunneling, maintenance cost, boards of directors pay, Chairman's pay, directors equity holding outside directors pay and CEO allowance

Abstract: *This study investigated the effect of directors tunneling on maintenance cost of information and communication technology service industries in Nigeria. The specific objectives were to examine the effect of boards of directors pay, Chairman's pay, directors equity holding outside directors pay and CEO allowance on maintenance cost of information and communication technology service in Nigeria. Ex-post facto research design was adopted in this study; The population of the study consists of nine information and communication technology firms, the researcher choose the entire nine firms to represent the sample size. The study also employed descriptive statistics, correlation test, variance inflation test, Panel Least Squared (PLS) method of data analysis was used. From the analysis result the study found that, Outside directors pay had insignificant and negative effect on maintenance cost of information and communication technology service in Nigeria ($t=-1.323954$, $p=0.1900$). CEO allowance have insignificant effect on maintenance cost of information and communication technology service in Nigeria ($t=, 0.782760$, $p=0.4365$). Boards of directors pay have significant and negative effect on maintenance cost of information and communication technology service in Nigeria. ($t=-3.151425$, $p=0.0024$). Chairman's pay had significant positive effect on maintenance cost of information and communication technology service in Nigeria ($t=, 2.913647=0.0049$). Chairman's pay had insignificant negative effect on maintenance cost of information and communication technology service in Nigeria ($t=-1.267569=0.2093$). The study concludes that directors tunneling have negative effect on maintenance cost of information and communication technology service in Nigeria. It was recommended that Outside directors pay*

Abazu M. Ebere and Prof., M.S Ifureze

should not be fixed by the executive directors rather it should be fixed by the entire shareholder during the annual general meeting to reduce the influence of the directors and the give and take politics of the board. Joint committee comprising of members of the board of director and selected shareholder be set up to review the proposed CEO allowance before the final approval by the entire members during the annual general meeting. Adequate management and controlling of board of director's pay should be pursued by the shareholders of the ICT companies in Nigeria.

1.1 Background to the Study

Over the years, in an attempt to reduce and ensure the conformity of executive interest to that of shareholders, government and other stakeholders had advocated for corporate governance guidelines and better incentive package to align both interests as these will enhance board accountability, transparency and better disclosure which can promote fairness and curb the effect of conflict in information and communication of interest between directors and shareholders. The major problems facing tunneling stems from the fact that it is an opportunistic behavior in which the controlling shareholders use their controlling power to transfer the company's assets and profits to their own (Johnson et al., 2010). This seriously undermines the minority shareholder's interests as well as exacerbates the Type II agency conflict.

Again, tunneling is not only detrimental to the interests of minority shareholders but also seriously precludes the development of the organization at large. Lastly, the exploitation of

minority shareholders by controlling shareholders, leads to a loss of the minority shareholders, whose ownership is lessened or otherwise devalued through inappropriate actions that harm the overall value of the business and therefore the value of the shares owned by the minority shareholders. Arifah, et al. (2023) looked at the influence of tunneling and GCG variables on the performance of Indonesian State-Owned Enterprises. The results of the data analysis showed that tunneling and GCG had a significant effect on the performance of Indonesian State-Owned Enterprises, both simultaneously and partially. Tanvir and Syed (2021) investigated an impact of family ownership (FOwn) on asset or general tunneling (TunG) and cash flow tunneling (TunCF). Results confirmed that family ownership impacts tunneling activities. Amon, Wei, Jing-Ming and Xiaoqi (2020) examined the monitoring effect of mutual funds on the tunneling behavior of controlling shareholders. Moreover, the above effects are found to be more pronounced for firms with

Abazu M. Ebere and Prof., M.S Ifureze

Advance Journal of Linguistics and Mass Communication

Adv. J. Lin. M. Com

Volume: 10; Issue: 02

March-April, 2026

ISSN: 5314-6414 (p);

5344-3692 (e)

Impact Factor: 6.17

Advance Scholars Publication

International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/Ajlmc/index>

heavier tunneling activities. The finding of the non-monotonic monitoring role of mutual funds brings attention to the private interest theory for mutual funds, an aspect that has been largely ignored in previous studies on mutual funds. Anah, Ogbodo and Akinroluyo, (2022) investigated the effect of directors' tunneling on financial performance of selected listed Deposit Money banks in Nigeria. The results show that for Deposit money banks in Nigeria, directors' remuneration has a positive insignificant effect on return on asset (financial performance). Okafor and Ifurueze (2019) examined the effect of directors tunneling on performance of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Board of director's pay and Chairman's pay are negative, and Dividend payment to directors is positive and has insignificant effect on performance of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

Against this backdrop, the present study uses an current literature, varied the independent variables as against the ones formerly used by some of the previous researchers. However the previous researchers adopted survey method. Most of the study was carried out in banking sector but the present study was conducted using information and communication technology firms which no study has covered to the best of the researcher knowleges. The present study will also extent the scope to 2023 which no study to the best of researcher's knowledge has done that.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of this study were to investigate the effect of directors tunneling on maintenance cost of information and communication technology service industries in Nigeria. The specific objective of the study includes the following, to;

- i. Examine the effect of outside directors pay on maintenance cost of information and communication technology service in Nigeria.
- ii. Investigate the effect of CEO compensation on maintenance cost of information and communication technology service in Nigeria.
- iii. Evaluate the effect of board directors pay on maintenance cost of information and communication technology service in Nigeria.
- iv. Ascertain the effect of charman's pay on maintenance cost of information and communication technology service in Nigeria.
- v. Ascertain the effect of directors equity holding on maintenance cost of information and communication technology service in Nigeria.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Directors' Tunneling

The term tunneling was first used in Czech Republic to refer to the expropriation of minority shareholders (as in removing assets through an underground tunnel) (Johnson et al., 2000) and to describe the transfer of assets and profits out of firms for the benefit of those who control them (Henemana & Schwab, 1972). Johnson et al., (2000) noted that tunneling includes the extracting of resources/wealth

Abazu M. Ebere and Prof., M.S Ifureze

Advance Journal of Linguistics and Mass Communication

Adv. J. Lin. M. Com

Volume: 10; Issue: 02

March-April, 2026

ISSN: 5314-6414 (p);

5344-3692 (e)

Impact Factor: 6.17

Advance Scholars Publication

International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/Ajlmc/index>

from a firm for personal gain by controlling shareholders. This term was used during the first half of the 1990s, when several large, previously privatized banks and factories unexpectedly went bankrupt.

Directors tunneling may involve the diversion of company assets or resources for personal use or to entities controlled by the directors. This could take the form of transferring company funds, equipment, or contracts to entities in which the directors have a financial interest. Directors may enter into related-party transactions that favor entities associated with them over the best interests of the company (Ntim, 2019). These transactions are often not conducted at arm's length and may result in the company paying inflated prices for goods or services. Directors' tunneling can also involve the misappropriation of business opportunities that rightfully belong to the company. Directors may withhold valuable information, divert potential deals, or engage in competitive activities that undermine the company's interests. Directors' tunneling often occurs in a non-transparent manner, with directors exploiting their positions of trust and authority to carry out self-serving actions without proper disclosure to other stakeholders (Nwanne, & Okonkwo, 2019). Directors' tunneling is a serious breach of fiduciary duty and corporate governance standards. It can erode shareholder value, damage the company's reputation, and undermine trust in the integrity of corporate leadership. Companies and

regulatory bodies must implement robust controls, oversight mechanisms, and ethical standards to prevent directors from engaging in tunneling practices and hold them accountable for any misconduct that occurs (Ogbechie, & Koufopoulos, 2020).

It was discovered later that the managements of these companies were deliberately transferring company property and real estate into their own private businesses, sometimes in offshore locations. The term later became a common label for this kind of criminal activity among Czechs and Slovaks. The transfers of firm resources were accomplished through huge loans that were issued without any expectation of repayment, massive overpayment for outsourced services, or simply by selling corporations real estate for a fraction of its market price (Ogbechie, Koufopoulos, & Argyropoulou, 2019). The main conditions enabling such an activity are weak law, conflict of interest, non-existent legal action against managers for leading their employer towards bankruptcy.

2.1.2 Maintenance cost

Maintenance cost refers to the expenses incurred to keep assets, equipment, and facilities in good working order. These are recurring, necessary costs for upkeep, including labor, parts, and materials, as opposed to one-time capital expenditures for major upgrades that extend an asset's life (Nzisa, Njeje, & Namiida, 2017). Proper tracking is essential for

Abazu M. Ebere and Prof., M.S Ifureze

Advance Journal of Linguistics and Mass Communication

Adv. J. Lin. M. Com

Volume: 10; Issue: 02

March-April, 2026

ISSN: 5314-6414 (p);

5344-3692 (e)

Impact Factor: 6.17

Advance Scholars Publication

International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/Ajlmc/index>

business budgeting, financial reporting, and performance analysis. Maintenance costs include all the direct and indirect expenses of upkeep, repairs, replacement, and all maintenance activities. Some costs – like the sticker price for new equipment – are obvious. Others are hidden, often accumulating unnoticed (Atikiya, Mukulu, Kihoro, & Waiganjo, 2015).

Maintenance costs refer to any expense incurred by an individual or corporation to keep its assets in operating condition. These expenditures may be necessary for routine maintenance, such as installing anti-virus software on computer systems or preventing degradation, such as repairing a vehicle (Fasua, & Osifo, 2020).. These costs are in addition to the asset's purchase cost. It's vital for people and businesses to incur them to keep their assets in good working order. Customers who acquire serviceable assets usually anticipate paying costs for maintenance in the future if they intend to use them for an extended period (Thomas, El-Hajjar, & Hanzo, 2015). The amount an individual pays in maintenance charges varies according to the type of asset and the frequency with which maintenance is necessary.

2.2. Theoretical Review

This study is anchored on Agency theory; the theory has been widely used in literature to investigate the information asymmetry between principals (shareholders) and agent (manageme

nt). This study uses the agency theory to determine the Directors Tunneling and Asset Utilization of information and communication technology Service in Nigeria. Sarens and Abdolmohammadi (2007), states that according to the agency theory, a company consists of a set of linked contracts between the owners of economic resources (the principals) and managers (the agents) who are charged with using and controlling these resources. Jensen and Meckling (1976), states that in agency theory, agents have more information than principals and this information asymmetry adversely affects the principals' ability to monitor whether or not their interests are being properly served by the agents.

Agency theory has been widely used in literature to investigate the information asymmetry between principals (shareholders) and agent (management). This study uses the agency theory to determine the Director Tunneling and Asset Utilization of information and communication technology Service in Nigeria. Sarens and Abdolmohammadi (2007), states that according to the agency theory, a company consists of a set of linked contracts between the owners of economic resources (the principals) and managers (the agents) who are charged with using and controlling these resources. Jensen and Meckling (1976), states that in agency theory, agents have more information than principals and this information asymmetry adversely affects the principals' ability to

Abazu M. Ebere and Prof., M.S Ifureze

Advance Journal of Linguistics and Mass Communication

Adv. J. Lin. M. Com

Volume: 10; Issue: 02

March-April, 2026

ISSN: 5314-6414 (p);

5344-3692 (e)

Impact Factor: 6.17

Advance Scholars Publication

International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/Ajlmc/index>

monitor whether or not their interests are being properly served by the agents. Jensen and Meckling (1976) opine that moral hazard constitutes a situation where to maximize their own wealth; agents may face the dilemma of acting against the interests of their principals. Since principals do not have access to all available information at the time a decision is being made by an agent, they are unable to determine whether the agent's actions are in the best interest of the firm. To reduce the likelihood of the moral hazard, principals and agents engage in contracting to achieve optimality, including the establishment of monitoring processes such as auditing.

Relevance of the theory to the Study

The principal-agent relationship in agency theory is important to understanding how the role of tunnelling on asset utilization. Principals appoint agents and delegate some decision making authority to them. In so doing, the principals place their trust in their agents to act in the principals' best interests. However, as a result of information asymmetries between principals and agents differing motives, principals may lack trust in their agents and may therefore need to put in place mechanisms, such as the internal auditor, to reinforce this trust.

2.3 Empirical Review

Nwaogu, Odesa and Nzoegbu (2019) evaluates the effect of director's tunneling on asset utilization of companies in consumer goods

sector in Nigeria using a panel data collected from annual financial report of thirty listed consumer goods firm in Nigeria between 2011 and 2016. The study was based on ex-post-fact research design and the data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics, correlation analysis and multiple regression. The study finds that the director 'spay and equity holding varies widely among consumer goods firms. Chairman's pay and director's equity holding have a statistically significant effect on asset utilization at 5% level. While the director's pay policy has no statistically significant effect on asset utilization. The finding shows pay, chairman's pay and director's equity holding are three major avenues used for tunneling as they have a significant effect on tunneling.

Gandhi and Olenski (2024) examined "tunneling" practices through which health care providers covertly extract profit by making inflated payments for goods and services to commonly-owned related parties. While incentives to tunnel exist across sectors, health care providers may find it uniquely advantageous to hide their profits and assets by shifting them to related parties. Understating profitability may dissuade regulators from imposing stricter quality standards and encourage public payers to increase reimbursement rates. Likewise, tunneling effectively "shields" assets from malpractice liability risk by moving them off the firm's balance sheet. We find evidence of widespread

Abazu M. Ebere and Prof., M.S Ifureze

Advance Journal of Linguistics and Mass Communication

Adv. J. Lin. M. Com

Volume: 10; Issue: 02

March-April, 2026

ISSN: 5314-6414 (p);

5344-3692 (e)

Impact Factor: 6.17

Advance Scholars Publication

International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/Ajlmc/index>

tunneling through inflated rents and management fees paid to related parties. Extrapolating these estimated markups to all firms' related party transactions suggests that in 2019, 68% of nursing home profits were hidden by tunneling to related parties through inflated transfer prices.

Arifah, et al. (2023) looked at the influence of tunneling and GCG variables on the performance of Indonesian State-Owned Enterprises. The data used is secondary data taken from the Annual Report of Indonesian State-Owned Enterprises. The data period is six years, from 2014 to 2019. The population in this study was 44 Indonesian State-Owned Enterprises, and the sample was determined using purposive sampling methods. The data is processed using multiple linear regression analysis. The results of the data analysis showed that tunneling and GCG had a significant effect on the performance of Indonesian State-Owned Enterprises, both simultaneously and partially. This study implies that more technical regulations are needed to regulate the boundaries of related transactions in State-Owned Enterprises so that tunneling actions can be minimized. State-Owned Enterprises must also always improve their performance to be more optimal, at least it can increase of State Owned Enterprises that can deposit dividends into the state treasury. The novelty of this research is the use of SOE objects for tunneling

subjects that are generally research in private companies.

Anah, et al, (2022) investigated the effect of directors' tunneling on financial performance of selected listed Deposit Money banks in Nigeria. A sample of 10 Deposit Money banks listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange for a period of 9 years (from 2012-2020) was selected. Secondary method of data collection was adopted; data was sourced from the Nigerian Stock Exchange fact book. This study applied the longitudinal research design. Data collected were analyzed using Ordinary Least Square regression Method. The results show that for Deposit money banks in Nigeria, directors' remuneration has a positive insignificant effect on return on asset (financial performance). This study therefore concluded that directors' tunneling have an insignificant positive effect on financial performance of selected listed Deposit Money banks in Nigeria and recommended that regulators should make it mandatory for listed banks to clearly show all the remunerations and bonuses in monetary value on the annual reports and accounts to enable stakeholders determine the extent to which shareholders wealth maximization objective is in pursuit, thereby reducing the possibility of corporate tunneling.

Okafor and Ifurueze (2019) examined the effect of directors tunneling on performance of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The study has four specific objectives to achieve, four

Abazu M. Ebere and Prof., M.S Ifureze

research questions that guided the study and four null hypotheses were formulated. The study used ex-post factor research design. Fifteen (15) firms were selected from the Nigeria Stock Exchange (NSE). The data used were secondary data and were drawn from 2008 to 2017. The secondary data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics, correlation and regression analysis. The data used in this study were sourced from the firm's annual report and Nigerian Stock Exchange fact book. This study applied ex post facto research design. The data collected were analyzed using Ordinary Least Square Method. The results show that only Director's equity holding is negative and has significant effect on performance of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Board of director's pay and Chairman's pay are negative, and Dividend payment to directors is positive and has insignificant effect on performance of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

This study adopted *ex-post facto* research design that focuses on secondary data. *Ex- post facto* research design, involves collecting and analyzing data about some variables which are already in place.

3.2 Population of the Study

The population of the study consists of nine (9 from Nigeria) Information And Communication Technology firms listed on the floor of the Nigerian Exchange Group and from 2015 to 31st

December 2024. They are Airtel Africa plc, Briclinks Africa plc, Chams holdings company plc, Courteville business solution, CWG plc, E-teanzact international plc, MTN Nigeria communication, NCR plc, Omatek ventures

3.3 Sample Size and Sampling Method

The researcher used nine (9) firms from Nigeria to represent the sample size for this study and data was collected from the published financial statements, of the nine (9) selected firm for a ten (10) years period spanning from 2015-2024. The researcher used the purposive sampling method, (that is the firm selected were those that filed their annual financial statements with NSE from 2015-2024 without missing any year). The selected firms are Airtel Africa plc, Briclinks Africa plc, Chams holdings company plc, Courteville business solution, CWG plc, E-teanzact international plc, MTN Nigeria communication, Omatek ventures.

3.4 Nature and Sources of Data

The study employed panel data set from the annual report and financial statement of information and communication technology service firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group. The panel covered a period of nine (9) years from 2015-2024, and a cross section of firms. It is a secondary data set.

3.5 Method of Data Analysis

The data collected was analyzed using the linear regression and Panel Least Square (PLS). The study's choice of Fixed/Random effect will be guided by the fact that it has optimal properties

which includes, linearity, neutrality, sufficient, least variance and mean square. These attributes, shows that the properties of the estimators can be obtained from any techniques, but the minimum variance property, distinguished the Panel Least Square (PLS) estimates as the best when compared with other linear estimates from other econometric techniques. This particular, property of small least variance is the reason for the popularity of the PLS method.

3.6 Model Specification

The study modified the work of Okafor and Ifurueze (2019) who examined the effect of directors tunneling on performance of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria

The model is stated thus:

$$ROA = F (DEH, BDP, CP, DY) \text{ ----- (i)}$$

ROA= Return on asset

BDP= Board director pay

CP=Chairman pay

DY = Dividend pay

3.7 Variables and their Measurement

s/n	Variables	Measurement	Sources
1	Maintenance cost (MC)	Direct Maintenance Costs plus indirect Maintenance Costs	
2	Outside directors Pay (OTD)	Log value of Outside directors Pay	Agbaja, Adelokun & Udi, (2016)
3	CEO Compensation	Log value of CEO Compensation	(Kun and Xing, 2012)

The model was modified to enable us look at the topic from another dimension. Thus we state our modified model as:

The model to be regressed in this study is presented in a functional form as follows

$$MC = F (OTDP, CEOC, BDP, CHP, DEH,) \text{ ----- (ii)}$$

Where;

MC = Mintenance cost

OTD = Outside directors

CEOC = CEO Compensation

BDP= Board director pay

CAP=Chairman pay

DEH= Directors equity holding

F= Funtional noation

Econometrics form

$$MC_{it} = B_0 + B_1 OTD_{it} + B_2 CEOC_{it} + B_3 BDP_{it} + B_4$$

$$CHP_{it} + B_5 DEH_{it} + u$$

B₀= constant

B₁-B₅ = parameters Coefficients to be estimated

it= lagged values

4	Board director pay (BDP)	Log value of Board director pay	Wanga and Lin, 2014)
5	Chairman pay (CAP)	Log value of Chairman's pay	(Chena, Wanga and Lin, 2014)
5	Directors equity holding (DEH)	Log value of director's equity holding	(Kun and Xing, 2012)

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

4.1.1 Descriptive Statistics Analysis

Table 4.1.1, which displays the number of observations, mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum values of the explained

variable, and each of the explanatory variables, provides the descriptive statistics for all the variables in the model. The descriptive data of the chosen service sector that comprise our sample are displayed in the table below.

Table 4.1 Directors tunneling and Maintenance cost

	MC	LOTD	LCEOC	LBDP	LCHP	LDEH
Mean	0.508025	11.93835	14.11050	13.08080	11.75997	16.69470
Median	0.420000	12.60066	13.57422	12.66303	10.63662	15.42495
Maximum	2.590000	14.94000	17.58730	20.49942	19.83516	21.62799
Minimum	0.050000	9.326789	12.57025	3.737670	3.234749	11.65169
Std. Dev.	0.432789	1.328143	1.132438	5.197788	5.250364	3.632182
Skewness	3.262631	-0.649721	0.268169	-0.151338	0.153783	-0.051560
Kurtosis	15.10603	2.223697	2.098774	1.812589	1.868118	1.498913
Jarque-Bera Probability	638.3308 0.000000	7.732788 0.020934	3.712048 0.156293	5.067756 0.079351	4.643167 0.098118	7.640648 0.021921
Sum	41.15000	967.0067	1142.950	1059.544	952.5578	1352.271
Sum Sq. Dev.	14.98448	141.1170	102.5932	2161.360	2205.305	1055.420
Observations	81	81	81	81	81	81

Source: Sources: Authors Computation 2026

The table above indicates that the mean of maintenance cost (MC) is .43% with standard deviation of .05% the minimum and maximum

values of 0.5% and 2.5% respectively. The mean value of outside directors pay (LOTDP) is 11% with standard deviation of 1% the minimum and maximum values of 9 and 14% respectively. The mean value of CEO Compensation (LCEOC)

Abazu M. Ebere and Prof., M.S Ifureze

Advance Journal of Linguistics and Mass Communication

Adv. J. Lin. M. Com

Volume: 10; Issue: 02

March-April, 2026

ISSN: 5314-6414 (p);

5344-3692 (e)

Impact Factor: 6.17

Advance Scholars Publication

International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/Ajlmc/index>

is 14% with standard deviation of 1%, the minimum and maximum values of 12% and 17% respectively. Board directors pay (LBDP) mean value is 13% with standard deviation of 5%, the minimum and maximum values of 3% and 20% respectively. The mean value of Chairman' pay (LCHP) mean value is at 11% with standard deviation of 5%, the minimum and maximum values of 3% and 19% respectively. The mean value of Directors equity holdings (LDEH) mean value is at 16% with standard deviation of 3%, the minimum and maximum values of 11% and 21% respectively.

These results suggest that the data are not widely dispersed from the mean because the standard deviations of all the variables are less than the mean values. Also, the skewness value of all the variables is close to zero except maintenance cost, it means that the distribution of the variables is symmetric in nature,. The Kurtosis values of all the variables is also closer

to 3, it indicates that the shape is a normal distribution, except directors equity holding. The P-value of Jarque-Bera test of all the variables is less than 5%, except CEO Compensation; However, Shao (2003) submits that normality of data does not in any way affect the inferential statistics estimate to the BLUE properties. (Best, Linear, Unbiased, Estimate)

4.2: Correlation Analysis

A square matrix that displays the correlation coefficients between two variables is called a correlation matrix. The strength and direction of a linear relationship between two variables are measured by correlation coefficients. Frequently used in multivariate analysis and statistics, a correlation matrix looks at the relationships between several variables. Therefore, in examining the association among the variables, we employed the Pearson correlation coefficient (correlation matrix) and the results are presented in the table 4.2 below.

**Table 4.2 Spearman Correlation
 Directors tunneling and Maintenance Cost
 Correlations**

			MC	LOTD	CEOC	BDP	CHP	DEH
Spearman's rho	MC	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.393**	.	.603**	.057	.281*
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000	.	.000	.615	.011
		N	81	81	81	81	81	81
	LOTD	Correlation Coefficient	.393**	1.000	.	.276*	.431**	.106
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.	.	.013	.000	.347
		N	81	81	81	81	81	81
	CEOC	Correlation Coefficient	.	.	1.000	.	.	.
		Sig. (2-tailed)
		N	81	81	81	81	81	81
	BDP	Correlation Coefficient	.603**	.276*	.	1.000	.232*	.548**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.013	.	.	.037	.000
		N	81	81	81	81	81	81
	CHP	Correlation Coefficient	.057	.431**	.	.232*	1.000	.573**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.615	.000	.	.037	.	.000
		N	81	81	81	81	81	81
	DEH	Correlation Coefficient	.281*	.106	.	.548**	.573**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.011	.347	.	.000	.000	.
		N	81	81	81	81	81	81

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Advance Journal of Linguistics and Mass Communication

Adv. J. Lin. M. Com

Volume: 10; Issue: 02

March-April, 2026

ISSN: 5314-6414 (p);

5344-3692 (e)

Impact Factor: 6.17

Advance Scholars Publication

International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/Ajlmc/index>

Source: Source: Sources: Authors Computation 2026

Maintenance cost is positively connected with four factors, outside directors pay (ODP), CEO compensation (CEOC), and Chairman Pay (CHP) but negatively correlated with directors equity holding (DEH), according to the correlation matrix table. The aforementioned findings demonstrate that the Maintenance cost (MC/OTDP=-0.39) and outside directors pay (OTDP), are positively correlated. Additionally, there is a high and positive correlation (MC/BDP = -0.60) between Maintenance cost and board of directors pay. There is a significant and positive correlation between Maintenance cost and chairman's pay (MC/CHP) = 0.57.

Directors equity holding (DEH), and Maintenance cost are strongly and negatively correlated (DEH/MC=-0.28). Additionally, a substantial and negative correlation was identified between OTD and CHP (0.43). None of the factors, nevertheless, was discovered to be greater than 0.80. That is, no two exploratory

variables had a perfect correlation. The highest correlation is between two variables which are highly correlated with (MC/BDP=-0.60) which indicate that multi collinearity is not a serious problem that would distort the regression result in the model used for analysis. A close look at the value of the Pearson correlation coefficient results revealed that all the variables are strongly associated with Maintenance cost.

Therefore, in checking for multicollinearity problem, the study noticed from the correlation table above that no two explanatory variables were perfectly correlated and thereby ruled out the case of having an outlier. This indicates the absence of multi-collinearity problem in the model used for the analysis. This also justifies the use of the Panel Least Square (PLS)

4.3 Hausman Test

To choose between these two regressions models, Hausman test can be run to examine whether the difference between the random effects regression and the fixed effects regression is zero.

Advance Journal of Linguistics and Mass Communication

Adv. J. Lin. M. Com

Volume: 10; Issue: 02

March-April, 2026

ISSN: 5314-6414 (p);

5344-3692 (e)

Impact Factor: 6.17

Advance Scholars Publication

International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/Ajlmc/index>

Correlated Random Effects - Hausman Test

Equation: Untitled

Test period random effects

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Period random	11.592046	5	0.0408

** WARNING: estimated period random effects variance is zero.

Period random effects test comparisons:

Variable	Fixed	Random	Var(Diff.)	Prob.
LOTD	-0.056992	-0.050554	0.000031	0.2446
LCEOC	0.036386	0.058604	0.000104	0.0291
LBDP	-0.076921	-0.069084	0.000046	0.2462
LCHP	0.061435	0.060260	0.000022	0.8020
LDEH	-0.022310	-0.010731	0.000017	0.0049

The decision rule for a Hausman test is to reject the null hypothesis if the p-value is less than your chosen significance level (typically 0.05), indicating a fixed effects model is more appropriate, and to fail to reject the null hypothesis if the p-value is greater than or equal

to the significance level, suggesting a random effects model is suitable. The null hypothesis typically posits that the independent variables are not correlated with the error terms, making a random effects model efficient and appropriate

MODEL : $MC_{it} = B_0 + B_1 OTD_{it} + B_2 CEOC_{it} + B_3 BDP_{it} + B_4 CHP_{it} + B_5 DEH_{it} + u$

Abazu M. Ebere and Prof., M.S Ifureze

Table 4.4 FIXED EFFECT

Dependent Variable: MC

Method: Panel Least Squares

Date: 08/31/25 Time: 13:06

Sample: 2015 2023

Periods included: 9

Cross-sections included: 9

Total panel (balanced) observations: 81

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.331154	0.990882	1.343404	0.1837
LOTD	-0.056992	0.043047	-1.323954	0.1900
LCEOC	0.036386	0.046485	0.782760	0.4365
LBDP	-0.076921	0.024408	-3.151425	0.0024
LCHP	0.061435	0.021085	2.913647	0.0049
LDEH	-0.022310	0.017600	-1.267569	0.2093

Effects Specification

Period fixed (dummy variables)

R-squared	0.755368	Mean dependent var	0.508025
Adjusted R-squared	0.710887	S.D. dependent var	0.432789
S.E. of regression	0.408089	Akaike info criterion	1.201257
Sum squared resid	11.15793	Schwarz criterion	1.615113
Log likelihood	-34.65092	Hannan-Quinn criter.	1.367302
F-statistic	9.767485	Durbin-Watson stat	1.947753
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000021		

The result also revealed that the R-squared value of 0.755368 which is equivalent to 75% approximately, it indicates that the independent variables explains about 75% of the systematic variation in the determinants of selected firms

over the 81 years period observed while the remaining 25% is explained outside the unspecified variables thereby captured by the error terms, thus, exogenously explained.

Abazu M. Ebere and Prof., M.S Ifureze

Advance Journal of Linguistics and Mass Communication

Adv. J. Lin. M. Com

Volume: 10; Issue: 02

March-April, 2026

ISSN: 5314-6414 (p);

5344-3692 (e)

Impact Factor: 6.17

Advance Scholars Publication

International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/Ajlmc/index>

The F-statistics measures the overall significance of the explanatory parameter. From the result report in table 4.4 above, our computed value of f-statistics is 9.767485, while its probability is 0.0002, given this value we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis which state that there is a significant relationship between the variance of estimated regression model.

A' priori criteria which is used to determine the existing economic theories and indicates the sign of the accounting parameter under consideration.

The coefficient of regression (-0.056992) indicates that outside directors pay has negative effect on maintenance cost. This indicates that a unit decrease in outside directors will lead to about 6 percent increase in the maintenance cost of ict firms.

Furthermore from the coefficient of regression (0.036386) indicates that CEO allowance has positive effect on maintenance cost. This indicates that a unit increase in CEO allowance will lead to about 4 percent increase in the maintenance cost of ICT firms.

From the coefficient table above, it was observe that board of directors pay has a negative sign givin its value as -0.076921, this implies that a unit increase in board of directors pay will increase the maintenance cost by 7%. This is not in line with apriori expectation.

However chairman;s pay has positive coefficient givin its value as 0.061435, this also implies

that, a unit increase in chairman's pay will eventually increase the maintenance cost by 6%, this conform to theoretical expectation.

Finally directors equity holder, it shows a negative value givin it figure as -0.022310, this portrys that a unit decrease in director equity holder will lead to an increase in maintenance cost by 2%, this does not conform to theoretical expection.

T-statistics, this is the measure used to determine the individual statistical significance of the variables in the model. From the model it was obtained that the outside directors pay has a negative signifcant effect (t-1.323954, p=0.1900) on maintenance cost, this further implies that outside directors pay has a persistant negative effect on maintenance cost of ICT firms in Nigeria.

Going further it was observred from the regression table above that CEO allowance has a postive signifcant effect (t, 0.782760, p=0.4365) on maintenance cost, this further implies that CEO allowance has a persistant postive effect on maintenance cost of ICT firms in Nigeria.

Moreso, it was observred from the regression table above that board directors pay has a negative insignifcant effect (t-3.151425, p=0.0024) on maintenance cost, this further implies that board directors pay has a persistant negative and signifcant effect on maintenance cost of ICT firms in Nigeria

Chairman's pay has a postive signifcant effect (t 2.913647, p=0.0049) on maintenance cost, this

Abazu M. Ebere and Prof., M.S Ifureze

further implies that Chairman's pay has significant effect on maintenance cost of ICT firms in Nigeria

Lastly, directors equity holding has a negative insignificant effect ($t=1.267569$, $p=0.2093$) on maintenance cost, this further implies that directors equity holding has no significant affect on maintenance cost of ICT firms in Nigeria

The Durbin-Watson statistics is used to test for the presence or otherwise of autocorrelation in our model. When the value of Durbin-Watson is closer or a little bit above 2, it means the absence of autocorrelation amongst the explanatory parameter (Koutsoyannis 1997) from the table 4.3 above, it was obtained that our Durbin-Watson result is (1.8), this satisfy the above stated condition. This means the absence of autocorrelation among the explanatory variables.

4.4 HYPOTHESES TESTING

Hypothesis One

Ho 1: Outside directors pay does not have significant effect on maintenance cost of information and communication technology service in Nigeria..

Drawing inference from our regression result in table 4.4 above, we found that the value of Outside directors pay is -1.323954, while its probability is 0.1900. This shows that Outside directors pay is negatively insignificant. Furthermore, since its probability (0.1900) is greather than 0.05% level of significance, we reject the alternative hypothesis (Ho) and

accept null hypothesis (H1) which says that Outside directors pay does not have significant effect on maintenance cost of information and communication technology service in Nigeria

Hypothesis Two

Ho2: CEO allowance does not have significant effect on maintenance cost of information and communication technology service in Nigeria.

From table 4.4 above, we found out that computed value for CEO allowance is -0.782760 while it's probability is 0.4365. This shows that the CEO allowance is postive and has insignificant effect at 5% level of significant. Based on this analysis, we reject (Hi) and accept (Ho), which implies that CEO allowance have no significant effect on maintenance cost of information and communication technology service in Nigeria

Hypothesis Three

Ho3: Board directors pay does not have significant effect on maintenance cost of information and communication technology service in Nigeria.

From table 4.4 above, we found out that computed value for Board directors pay is -3.151425, while its probability is 0.0024. This shows that the Board directors pay is statistically significant at 5% level of significant. Based on this analysis, we accept (Hi) and reject (Ho), which implies that Board directors pay have significant effect on maintenance cost of

information and communication technology service in Nigeria

Hypothesis Four

H04: Chairman's pay does not have significant effect on maintenance cost of information and communication technology service in Nigeria.

From table 4.4 above, we found out that computed value for Chairman's pay is 2.913647, while its probability is 0.000. This shows that the Chairman's pay is statistically significant at 5% level. Based on this analysis, we accept (H₁) and reject (H₀), which implies that Chairman's pay have significant effect on maintenance cost of information and communication technology service in Nigeria

Hypothesis Five

H05: Directors equity holding does not have significant effect on maintenance cost of information and communication technology service in Nigeria.

Drawing inference from our regression result in table 4.4 above, we found that the value of Directors equity holding is -1.267569, while its probability is 0.2093. This shows that Directors equity holding is positively insignificant. Furthermore, since its probability (0.2093) is greater than 0.05% level of significance, we reject the alternative hypothesis (H₁) and accept null hypothesis (H₀), which says that Directors equity holding have no significant effect on maintenance cost of information and communication technology service in Nigeria

CONCLUSION

AND

RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1: Conclusion:

It therefore concludes that, director's tunneling has a negative effect on the maintenance cost of ICT companies in Nigeria

5.2: Recommendations

On the basis of the findings and conclusions of the study the paper recommends among others that:

- i. Outside directors pay should not be fixed by the executive directors rather it should be fixed by the entire shareholder during the annual general meeting to reduce the influence of the directors and the give and take politics of the board.
- ii. Joint committee comprising of members of the board of director and selected shareholder be set up to review the proposed CEO allowance before the final approval by the entire members during the annual general meeting.
- iii Management and controlling of board of director's pay is therefore an important factor to be considered in enhancing or boosting the performance of ICT in Nigeria. It is therefore necessary that adequate management and controlling of board of director's pay should be pursued by the shareholders of the ICT companies in Nigeria. This can be achieved by specifying the terms and conditions of the board of director's pay in the annual general meeting of the shareholders

Abazu M. Ebere and Prof., M.S Ifureze

Advance Journal of Linguistics and Mass Communication

Adv. J. Lin. M. Com

Volume: 10; Issue: 02

March-April, 2026

ISSN: 5314-6414 (p);

5344-3692 (e)

Impact Factor: 6.17

Advance Scholars Publication

International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/Ajlmc/index>

.iv. proper control should be emphasized on the chairman's pay by the shareholders of ICT companies in order to prevent fraud.

REFERENCES

Amon, C., Wei J., Jing-Ming, K. & Xiaoqi S. (2020) Mutual funds, tunneling and firm performance: evidence from China. *Review of Quantitative Finance and Accounting* (2020) 55:355–387

Anah, A.S, Ogbodo, O.C Akinroluyo B. I. (2025) "Effect of Directors' Tunneling on Financial Performance of Selected Listed Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria" Published in *International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development* (ijtsrd), 6 (2) 152-159

Arif, S., Marshall, N., Yohn, T.L., (2016). Understanding the relation between accruals and volatility: A real options-based investment approach. *Journal of Accounting and Economics* 62 (1), 65–86.

Arifah, S., Rahmawati, Agung N. P., Setianingtyas H., Sri H. , Sri M., & Kiswanto, (2023) Tunneling Control and Good Corporate Governance to Improve State Owned Enterprise Performance. *AKRUAL: Jurnal Akuntansi*, 14(2), 191-202 DOI: 10.26740/jaj.v14n2.p191-202

v. The study therefore recommends that a higher equity holding may lead to higher assets utilization for ICT companies in Nigeria..

Atikiya, R. U. K. I. A., Mukulu, E., Kihoro, J., & Waiganjo, E. (2015). Effect of cost leadership strategy on the performance of manufacturing firms in Kenya. *Journal of Management*, 2(8), 134-143.

Gandhi, A. and Olenski, A. (2024) Tunneling and Hidden Profits in Health Care NBER Working Paper No. 32258

Henemana, S. & Schwab, C. (1972). Tunnelling, propping, and expropriation: evidence from connected party transactions in Hong Kong. *Journal of Financial Economics* 82 (2), 343 - 386.

Johnson, S., LaPorta, R., Lopez-de-Silanes, F., & Shleifer, A., 2000, Tunneling. *The American Economic Review*, Vol. 90(No. 2), 22-27.

Ntim, C. G. (2019). An integrated corporate governance framework and financial performance in South African- listed corporations. *South African Journal of Economics*, 81(3), 373-392

Nwanne, T.F.I. & Okonkwo, E. J. (2019). Corporate board characteristics and deposit money banks (DMB)

Abazu M. Ebere and Prof., M.S Ifureze

Advance Journal of Linguistics and Mass Communication

Adv. J. Lin. M. Com

Volume: 10; Issue: 02

March-April, 2026

ISSN: 5314-6414 (p);

5344-3692 (e)

Impact Factor: 6.17

Advance Scholars Publication

International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/Ajlmc/index>

performance in Nigeria for the period 2008-2017. *Archives of Business Research*, 7(5), 75-95.

Nzisa, J., Njeje, D., & Namiida, B. (2017). Influence of Cost Leadership Strategy on Growth of Hotel Chains: A Perspective from the Kenyan Context. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*, 19(12), 64-71.

Ogbechie, C., Koufopoulos, D, N. &Argyropoulou, M. (2019). Board characteristics and involvement in strategic decision making: The Nigerian perspective. *Management Research News*, 32,(3) 169-184.

Okafor, J. I. & Ifurueze, M. S. (2019) Effect of Director's Tunneling on Performance of Quoted Manufacturing Companies in Nigeria. *Journal of accounting, business and social sciences* 2(1), 1-10

Tanvir A. & Syed M. A. T. (2021) Family-Owned Firms and Tunneling Effect: An Evidence from South Asian, Lower-Middle Income, Frontier Market Index Economy. *International Journal Management (IJM)*12(3), 1176-1188

Abazu M. Ebere and Prof., M.S Ifureze